

Encarsia formosa, a larval parasite of other whiteflies. Identification of the whitefly collected at Ibadan was verified by L. M. Russell, U.S. Department of Agriculture at Beltsville, Maryland, and D. J. Williams, Commonwealth Institute of Entomology (CIE). The parasite was identified by A. Polaozek of CIE. □

A method for rearing armyworm *Spodoptera mauritia acronyctoides* Guenée (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) on graminaceous hosts

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Armyworms often are reared in petri dishes with moistened paper towel and cut rice leaves to track development of individuals. But this method entails changing of plants and removing fecal material daily and is unreliable. Also larval survival is low because of high levels of fungal or bacterial infections.

We have designed a setup to minimize these disadvantages (see figure).

One-mo-old host plants are uprooted. Individual tillers are separated, wrapped

Improved method for rearing armyworm. IIRRI, 1988.

with moistened cotton, and placed in 10.5- × 2.5-cm test tubes. A cardboard plug prevents larvae from drowning.

Each test tube with plant is enclosed in a 19- × 4-cm cylindrical mylar cage with nylon mesh vents on the side and top. Nylon mesh attached to the base of the cylinder traps fecal material and aerates it to prevent fungal or bacterial infection.

One first-instar larva is placed on each host plant, using a moist camel hair brush. Caged plants with larvae are held upright in a wooden rack. (We use a compartmentalized 47- × 85-cm seedbox to accommodate 60 setups.) Plants are replaced every 3 d.

Average pupation of *S. m. acronyctoides* larvae was higher with this method than with using petri dishes (see table). □

Simulated yellow stem borer (YSB) population dynamics: sensitivity and application

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We analyzed the sensitivity of a simulation model of YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* population dynamics (SIMYSB) to changes in structure and parameter values.

For coarse sensitivity analysis, five mortality factors—egg predation; plant age; and parasitization of eggs, larvae, and pupae—were sequentially omitted from the model, to determine their significance for YSB larval population dynamics. Fine sensitivity analysis involved increasing and decreasing development, immigration, and oviposition rates by 20% to determine their relative importance in the system.

Without the effects of egg predation, egg parasitization, or plant age, larval population fluctuated at a relatively high level in both generations (Fig. 1). Without larval or pupal parasitization, the fluctuating level was relatively low, particularly in the first generation. On the whole, egg predators, egg parasites, and plant age are the most important factors regulating YSB populations.

Pupation of *Spodoptera mauritia acronyctoides* reared on graminaceous host plants. IIRRI laboratory and greenhouse, Jun-Jul 1988.

Plant	Pupation ^a (%)	
	Petri dish method	Whole plant method
<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	0	100 ± 0
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook f.	20 ± 0.45	100 ± 0
<i>E. colona</i> (L.) Link	40 ± 0.55	100 ± 0
<i>Brachiaria distachya</i> (L.) Stapf.	20 ± 0.45	80 ± 0.45
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) Beauv. ssp. <i>hispidula</i> (Retz.) Honda	40 ± 0.55	80 ± 0.45
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i> Berg.	40 ± 0.55	80 ± 0.45
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i> (L.) Nees	20 ± 0.45	60 ± 0.55
\bar{X}	26 ± 0.15	86 ± 0.15

^a Av of 5 replications.

1. Effect of omitting different mortality factors on simulated YSB larval populations in 1987 WS. 1 = with all effects (reference model), 2 = without egg predation, 3 = without egg parasitization, 4 = without effect of plant ages on larval survival, 5 = without larval parasitization, 6 = without pupal parasitization.

Response of larval populations to changes in egg, larval, and pupal development rates was highly proportional and asymmetrical (Fig. 1). This implies that rates are important variables, because they have large, complex effects on the system. Changes in immigration rate brought about an exactly proportional (20%) and symmetrical ($\pm 20\%$) effect on insect population across the season (Fig. 2b). Response to changes in oviposition rate was highly proportional but

2. Effect on YSB larval populations in 1987 WS of small changes in development rate (a), immigration rate (b), and oviposition rate (c).

semisymmetrical (Fig. 2c); a 20% alteration brought about the same amount of absolute changes in the first peak density but resulted in a higher increase (45.7%) in the second.

SIMYSB has been designed for application in YSB management. The user or researcher may choose to investigate single or combined common pest control tactics. Novel control strategies examined using the computer may lead to the design of useful field experiments. □

Life cycle of *Micraspis* sp. on brown planthopper (BPH) and rice pollen

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The coccinellid *Micraspis crocea* (Mulsant) feeds on plants and on leafhoppers and other small insect pests of rice. It also has been observed feeding on rice flower pollen. Beetles are

abundant in ricefields and could help suppress populations of several insect pests.

But because they feed on pollen, many farmers consider them a pest and often spray insecticides to control them.

We studied *M. crocea* in the greenhouse, using the BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) and flowering rice panicles. Adult beetles collected from fields were caged on TN1 rice plants with BPH nymphs. Beetle eggs collected daily were placed in petri dishes lined with moist filter paper to determine incubation time. Individual larvae were placed in 2- × 20-cm glass vials with rice stems and second- and third-instar BPH. We reared 75 larvae using this procedure.

Another set of 75 larvae were reared in vials containing flowering rice panicles. Panicles and BPH were changed daily. Ladybeetle larvae were observed to determine time between stages, pupation period, and emergence of adults. Newly emerged adults were reared on both rice panicles and BPH to

Simulated yellow stem borer (YSB) population dynamics: modeling and evaluation

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A simulation model of YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* population dynamics (SIMYSB) was constructed using the state variable approach and boxcar train technique.

YSB population dynamics in a farmer's field were compared to model output for 1987 wet season (WS) and 1988 dry season (DS). A 2,500-m² field in Calauan, Laguna, Philippines, was transplanted with C168 (local long-duration variety susceptible to YSB) and not treated with insecticides. The field was subdivided into 50 plots.

Weekly pest sampling started shortly after transplanting. Each week, all plants in three plots selected at random were examined for adult moths and egg masses; 25% of the plants were sampled for dissection.

Biology of *Micraspis* sp. on BPH nymphs and flowering panicles. IRRI greenhouse, 1988.

Stage	Developmental period on ^a (d)	
	BPH nymphs	Flowering panicles
Incubation period	4.0 ± 0	4.0 ± 0
1st instar	3.2 ± 0.07	3.35 ± 0.08
2d instar	3.4 ± 0.11	3.3 ± 0.15
3d instar	4.2 ± 0.17	4.4 ± 0.18
4th instar	4.4 ± 0.14	7.1 ± 0.24
Pupal stage	4.0 ± 0	4.0 ± 0
Egg to adult	23.1 ± 0.33	26.1 ± 0.38
Adult longevity	94.4 ± 4.41	74.47 ± 3.57

^aMean of 75 insects ± standard error.

determine longevity.

In general, *Micraspis* sp. survived and developed successfully on both pollen and BPH (see table). This could explain why this beetle is so abundant during rice flowering and during BPH outbreaks. More detailed studies are underway to determine the effects of rice pollen feeding.

1. Simulated and farmer's field YSB egg, larval, and pupal populations, Calauan, Philippines, 1987 WS. First-instar larvae were excluded.